

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Generating 3D Cells Inside Anatomical Structures

How to use the 3D Cell Generation API for filling a 3D anatomical structure with cells

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Introduction

The Human Reference Atlas (Börner et al. 2025, 2021) provides a quantitative 3D framework of cell types across reference organs and 3D anatomical structures. The HRA Cell Type Population (HRApop) effort (Bueckle, Herr, Chen, et al. 2025) presents scalable workflows to (1) identify high-quality single-cell datasets, and (2) compute cell type annotations for them using Azimuth (Hao et al. 2021), CellTypist (Domínguez Conde et al. 2022; Xu et al. 2023), and/or popV (Ergen et al. 2024). To date, 662 datasets have been used for HRApop, resulting in cell populations for 73 anatomical structures within 17 organs. Out of these 662 datasets, 104 datasets contain sc-proteomics assay types with spatially explicit sc-data (meaning they have an X, Y, and optionally a Z-position if 3D). The remaining 558 datasets are scRNAseq datasets without spatial locations for cells. Cell positioning for these 558 datasets and multiple spatial omics datasets can be simulated using the 3D cell generation API.

By using mesh-based collision detection, the HRApop effort computes intersection percentages for each high-quality dataset in HRApop (Bueckle, Herr, Chen, et al. 2025), i.e., how much the total volume of the extraction site overlaps with each anatomical structure that it collides with. The resulting cell type populations for anatomical structures, or ASpop, is one of the major data products of HRApop. However, this data only contains the number (raw count and percentage) and type of cells for each anatomical structure (plus biomarker expression values which might be visualized in future work. For 3D visualization, each cell needs a 3D coordinate inside a scene node of a GLB file representing a 3D reference object for an organ. To address this, the 3D Cell Generation API was implemented (called 3DCG API in this SOP). This SOP details how the 3DCG API can be utilized to enable 3D visualization of cells within anatomical structures and how the HRA team ensures that the most up to date HRApop release data is available to the user via the 3DCG API.

The primary audiences for this SOP are developers and researchers who would like to use HRApop for 3D visualization inside 3D reference objects of the HRA. This SOP assumes basic

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

working knowledge of how to utilize RESTful APIs. Roles and responsibilities for those with a part in the procedures are listed in **Table 1**.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **HRA Technical Lead** oversees the implementation and maintenance of the 3DCG API and ensures that it utilizes the most recent HRApop release.

The **HRApop Lead** guides the acquisition of scientific data, directs the computation of HRApop values, and documents the results of each HRApop run, including documenting the datasets downloaded, annotated, and used for atlas construction. The HRApop Lead typically serves as first point of contact for users encountering issues with the 3DCG API, either on the scientific or technical level, relays issues to the HRA Technical Lead, and communicates solutions to the user.

The **User** employs the 3DCG API to generate 3D cell positions for a cell type population. This is typically one step in preparing data for 3D visualization (Bueckle et al. 2023; Kumar et al., n.d.).

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
HRA Technical Lead	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@iu.edu
HRApop Lead	Andreas Bueckle	abueckle@iu.edu
User	various	various

Relevant Resources

Table 2. Resources used in these procedures.

Name	Purpose	Location
HRA API proxy for the 3DCG API	Used to generate 3D cell positions	https://apps.humanatlas.io/api#post-/v1/mesh-3d-cell-population
HRA GLB Processor	Used to generate OFF files for 3D objects	https://github.com/cns-iu/hra-glb-pre-processor
Demo of the 3D Cell Generation API	Jupyter Notebook documenting use of the API	https://github.com/cns-iu/hra-pop-notebooks/blob/main/3d-cell-generation-usage/3d-cell-generation-usage.ipynb

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

hra_jupyter_widgets	Displays 3D result	https://github.com/x-atlas-consortia/hra-jupyter-widgets
sample cell type distribution	A sample cell type population in the form of a dictionary with key-value pairs of cell labels and a percentage between 0 and 1	https://github.com/cns-iu/hra-pop-notebooks/blob/main/3d-cell-generation-usage/example_cell_type_distribution.json
list of organs	Full listing of HRA organs	https://apps.humanatlas.io/api#get-v1/reference-organs

Procedures

Ensuring the latest HRApop data is served to the User

- The HRA Technical Lead and the HRApop Lead ensure that the code for the 3DCG API is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/cns-iu/hra-3d-cell-generation-api>.
- Once the 3DCG API is built, the HRA Technical Lead deploys it to Amazon Web Services (AWS) so that the HRA API provides the endpoint at <https://apps.humanatlas.io/api#post-v1/mesh-3d-cell-population> and proxies the user request to the AWS.
- To enable rapid querying of 3D reference objects and the 3D anatomical structures inside them, the HRA Technical Lead uses the [HRA GLB Processor](#) to generate Object File Format (OFF) files for each 3D reference object. These are files that retain the geometry, i.e., vertices and edges, but none of the materials that are part of the official HRA digital objects (DOs). OFF files are recomputed with every HRA release.
- These OFF files are then made available on the HRA Content Delivery Network (CDN) (Bueckle, Herr, Hardi, et al. 2025) for rapid, scalable usage.

Using the the 3DCG API to spatially position a particular cell type population in 3D

- The HRA API proxy for the 3DCG API is documented at <https://apps.humanatlas.io/api#post-v1/mesh-3d-cell-population>.
- The usage of the 3DCG API is documented in a [Jupyter Notebook](#). Concretely, this notebook demonstrates how to use the HRA API to get ASpop data for renal pyramid A in the male, left kidney, annotated by Azimuth, then uses the 3DCG API to get 3D cell positions for 10,000 cells for the top 10 cell types in the ASpop, then displays the 3D result using [HRA Jupyter Widgets](#).
- After installing the necessary Python packages, compile a cell type population in the form of a dictionary with key-value pairs of cell labels and a percentage between 0 and 1, see [this example file](#).

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

- Provide the GLB download link for the organ of interest, the node name of the required 3D anatomical structure (e.g., VH_M_renal_pyramid_a), and the total number of desired cells. See <https://apps.humanatlas.io/api#get-/v1/reference-organs> for a full listing of organs. **Fig. 1** shows the renal pyramid A of the left, male kidney without cells.

Figure 1. Renal pyramid A of the male, left kidney. This screenshot was taken inside Babylon.js at <https://sandbox.babylonjs.com/?assetUrl=https://cdn.humanatlas.io/digital-objects/ref-organ/kidney-male-left/v1.3/assets/3d-vh-m-kidney-l.glb>.

- The 3DCG API needs a user-provided payload.
 - Provide the organ link, 3D anatomical structure node name, and maximum number of cells. These require simple string or integer input.
 - Compile the CT population. Refer to the notebook for specific instructions. It demonstrates how the grlc.io query at https://apps.humanatlas.io/api/grlc/hra-pop.html#get-/cell_types_in_anatomical_structurescts_per_as can be used to retrieve ASpop for all AS in HRApop v1.0.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

- Then, using pandas, a Python library for data analysis and wrangling, the notebook filters keep only those cells that are in the male, left kidney, annotated by Azimuth, and in the 3D AS of interest.
- Finally, the data frame is transformed into a list of dictionaries that can be used as a parameter for the node-dist-vis in the [HRA Jupyter Widgets](#). See **Fig. 2** for an example that illustrates 10,000 cells using the 10 most common cell types in renal pyramid A of the male, left kidney.

Figure 2. The 3DCG API was used to generate the 3D positions of 10,000 cells, representing the 10 most common cell types (top-3: cortical thick ascending limb cell in red, descending thin limb type 1 cell in dark green, and cortical collecting duct principal cell in dark pink), in renal pyramid A of the left male kidney shown in **Fig. 1**. This screenshot was captured from within the [Jupyter Notebook](#).

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

The result can be exported as a CSV file for downstream usage in the Cell Distance Explorer (Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center 2024) and the HRA Organ Gallery (Kumar et al., n.d.).

References and Resources

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Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

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Glossary

Anatomical Structure Cell Type Populations (ASpop): A collection of cell type annotations for a specific anatomical structure, which captures the number of cells per cell type. Metadata includes an ontology ID, donor sex, anatomical structure label, the cell type annotation tool used to assign cell types, and a list of datasets from which the data was sourced.

application programming interface (API): Software that allows two applications to communicate with each other.

cell type population: A list of the cell types included in a collection of cell at different scales, such as an anatomical structure, extraction site, or dataset. Currently in the Human Reference Atlas, cell type populations consist of a listing of unique cell types, the number of cells per cell type, and mean biomarker expression values per cell type.

Human Reference Atlas Cell Type Populations (HRApop): HRApop is a standardized 3D dataset linking high-quality experimental data to Human Reference Atlas digital objects. HRApop quantifies the number of cells per cell type within anatomical structures, extraction sites, and datasets while harmonizing cell type annotations using crosswalks to common ontologies. HRApop is published as versioned releases and serves as a healthy reference for researchers aiming to clarify mechanisms underlying cellular interactions as well as cellular and tissue level disease progression.

Object File Format (OFF): Used to represent 3D geometry through polygons of the model surface with any number of vertices. You can see an example of an OFF file at https://shape.cs.princeton.edu/benchmark/documentation/off_format.html.

pandas: An open-source Python library for data analysis and manipulation (pandas.pydata.org).

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Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

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